

SELF-ASSESSMENT, STUDY HABITS, AND NUMERICAL ABILITIES ON THE MATHEMATICS LEARNING PRODUCTIVITY OF MATHEMATICS STUDENTS

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Self-Assessment, Study Habits, and Numerical Abilities on the Mathematics Learning Productivity of Mathematics Students

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Abstract

The purpose of the study is to determine the influence of self-assessment, study habits, and numerical abilities on the mathematics learning productivity of mathematics students. The study is quantitative research that utilizes multiple linear regression approach. A sample of 152 randomly selected mathematics major in KCAST students that was identified using stratified random sampling answered the surveys on the four variables. Results showed that the level of self-assessment, study habits, numerical abilities and mathematics learning productivity are all high in level. Result showed that there is significant relationship between self-assessment and mathematics learning productivity. In addition, there is also significant relationship between study habits and mathematics learning productivity. Likewise, there is also significant relationship between numerical abilities and mathematics learning productivity of the mathematics major students. Moreover, results show that domains of self- assessment such as previous education and expectations, emotions and confidence, general abilities and mathematical awareness and self-assessment of specific mathematical skills can significantly influence mathematics learning productivity. Further, it was revealed that domains of study habits such as note taking, use of library and time allocation to study can significantly influence mathematics learning productivity. Finally, results showed that there are domains of numerical abilities such as numerical reasoning, numerical logic, numerical arithmetic, numerical estimation and data interpretation that significantly predict mathematics learning productivity of the mathematics major students.

Keywords: *self-assessment, study habits, numerical abilities, mathematics learning productivity, mathematics major students*

Introduction

The efficiency and effectiveness with which students acquired mathematics is measured by their mathematics learning productivity. It is frequently described in terms of how long it takes students to pick up new ideas, how many problems they can answer correctly, and how deeply they comprehend mathematical ideas. Only 38% of fourth graders and 24% of eighth graders, respectively, achieved a score at or above the proficient level on the 2019 mathematics assessment, according to the National Assessment of Educational Progress (NAEP). This implies that a large number of students are not learning mathematics at a pace that will enable them to succeed in higher education and the workforce (NAEP, 2022)

In Indonesia, information was received from mathematics study teachers that the average value of students from the Mid semester test results has average mean of 54.78. This demonstrates that students' mathematics learning outcomes in these schools have yet to be sufficient. Low student learning outcomes for mathematics subjects are caused by a variety of factors, including students' lack of motivation to learn mathematics, as well as teachers' use of teaching methods that do not always correspond to the characteristics of mathematics. Students are primarily receivers and recipients of information from teachers, however the methods utilized by teachers in the process of learning mathematics are one of the decisive elements in boosting students' learning success (Ng, 2018).

In the Philippines, the same problem is also evident, wherein mathematics learning productivity needs to improve. According to the 2022 Programme for International Student Assessment (PISA) results, it shows that in the 2022 assessment, the students from the Philippines received average scores for math, reading, and science across participating countries, which were 472, 476, and 485, respectively. Unfortunately, the Philippines scored much lower than these averages, with scores of 355 in math, 347 in reading, and 373 in science—a significant difference of about 120 points. This means that students in the Philippines are falling behind global academic standards. The report reveals that Filipino students still rank among the weakest in the world in these subjects, with less than a quarter reaching the minimum proficiency level. This lack of improvement since 2018 and the country's performance below the global average highlight a significant challenge. The slow recovery from pandemic-related school closures has worsened the situation, leading to learning losses and difficulties in basic skills like reading. The Department of Education had expected this outcome and expressed concern. These results emphasize the urgent need for focused reforms and strategies to improve math learning in the Philippines (Chi, 2023).

As such, studying this concern is essential since it is an important problem that has to be solved, and research is required. Mathematics learning productivity are a significant concern owing to their wide-ranging impact on students, educators, and society as a whole. Students' capacity to understand and apply mathematical concepts, which is essential for problem-solving, critical thinking, and logical reasoning, is hindered by insufficient learning outcomes in mathematics. This problem is especially concerning because mathematics is a foundational subject in many fields, such as science, technology, engineering, and finance, and because poor mathematical abilities can significantly restrict an individual's career options. The study aims to investigate the impact of self-assessment, study habits, and

numerical abilities on mathematical learning productivity. By conducting this research, we can understand how these factors contribute to students' performance in mathematics. Identifying the influential factors will provide valuable insights for educators, parents, and policymakers to develop effective strategies and interventions to enhance mathematical learning productivity.

In connection, the researcher has not come to any studies about the effect of self-assessment, study habits, and numerical abilities on mathematics learning productivity in local settings. There have been studies conducted such as the studies Schoenberg (2018) a longitudinal study, Andrade & Tang, (2020) a systematic review and Van de Pol, Brand-Gruwel and Volman (2018) a randomized controlled trial, which focus on learning mathematics, numerical abilities and self-assessment but not on the effect of self-assessment, study habits, and numerical abilities on mathematics learning productivity and the respondents are not college education students. These studies are different from my own study given the fact that this research study does correlate about the effect of self-assessment, study habits, and numerical abilities on mathematics learning productivity. Moreover, It is based on the premise that the researcher felt it was necessary to conduct this study to determine the effect of self- assessment, study habits, and numerical abilities on mathematics learning productivity of mathematics students.

This research study intends to disseminate the findings of my research study on self-assessment, study habits and numerical abilities on the mathematics learning productivity of mathematics students through hardbound copies distributed strategically within our academic community. Coordinating with the research office to arrange a formal presentation and distribute hardbound copies to faculty and staff during the event, fostering direct engagement and discussions. Additionally, ensuring that hardbound copies are prominently available in the library, making them easily accessible to students and researchers.

Research Objectives

The main purpose of this study is to determine the significant relationship between self-assessment, study habits, and numerical abilities on the mathematics learning productivity among mathematics major students at Kapalong College of Agriculture, Sciences and Technology. Specifically, the objectives are the following:

1. To describe the level of self-assessment in mathematics learning productivity among mathematics major students at Kapalong College of Agriculture, Sciences, and Technology in terms of:
 - 1.1. previous education and expectations;
 - 1.2. emotions and confidence;
 - 1.3. general abilities and mathematical awareness; and
 - 1.4. self-assessment of specific mathematical skills.
2. To describe the level of study habits of students in terms of:
 - 2.1. note taking;
 - 2.2. use of library; and
 - 2.3. time allocation to study.
3. To describe the level of numerical abilities of students in terms of:
 - 3.1. numerical reasoning;
 - 3.2. numerical logic;
 - 3.3. numerical arithmetic;
 - 3.4. numerical estimation; and
 - 3.5. data interpretation.
4. To describe the level of mathematics learning productivity of students in terms of:
 - 4.1. persistence;
 - 4.2. engagement;
 - 4.3. collaboration; and
 - 4.4. communication.
5. To determine the significant relationship between:
 - 5.1. self-assessment and mathematics learning productivity;
 - 5.2. study habits and mathematics learning productivity; and
 - 5.3. numerical abilities and mathematics learning productivity.
6. To determine which domain/s of self-assessment, study habits, and numerical abilities that can influence mathematics learning productivity.

Methodology

Research Design

This study employs a quantitative multiple linear regression research design to evaluate the impact of self-assessment, study habits, and numerical abilities on the mathematics learning productivity of mathematics students. This approach is used to estimate the relationship between two or more independent variables and one dependent variable (Bevans, 2023).

Multiple linear regression, often referred to as just multiple regression, is a statistical method that predicts the value of a response variable using several explanatory variables. The goal is to model the linear relationship between the explanatory (independent) factors and the response (dependent) variables. As multiple regression incorporates more than one explanatory variable, it serves as an extension of ordinary least-squares regression (Hayes, 2023).

Quantitative researchers typically use questionnaires to collect data, asking respondents to report on attitudes, experiences, demographics, and other relevant information. This method relies on deductive logic, wherein researchers begin with hypotheses and then gather data to test these hypotheses. Through this process, researchers can predict future events based on current knowledge (Labaree, 2019).

Respondents

The respondents of this study were mathematics major students at Kapalong College of Agriculture, Sciences, and Technology (KCAST) during the first semester of

A.Y. 2023–2024. They were chosen as the respondents because the study was about the effect of self-assessment, study habits, and numerical abilities on the mathematics learning productivity of students. Since the study's purpose involved mathematics learning productivity, choosing mathematics students at Kapalong College of Agriculture, Sciences, and Technology (KCAST) was fitting and valid. Further, to establish randomness and maintain the element of science in the study, stratified random sampling was chosen.

One possible method is stratified random sampling. This approach divided the population into subgroups or strata based on relevant characteristics such as age, gender, and academic performance, and randomly selected samples from each stratum. Stratified random sampling helps ensure that the sample is representative of the population and that each subgroup is adequately represented, potentially increasing the generalizability of the results. However, this method required that the population be well-defined and the relevant characteristics for stratification known (Etikan & Bala, 2017).

Stratified random sampling is particularly appropriate for this study because respondents are randomly selected based on strata. In this case, they are mathematics major students at Kapalong College of Agricultural Sciences and Technology (KCAST).

To calculate the sample, the researcher first collected data about the respondent population by writing a formal request to the university's student office for access to the respondent population. After receiving the data, the researcher sent this information to a statistician who calculated the study sample.

Table 1. *Distribution of Respondents*

<i>Respondents</i>	<i>Population</i>	<i>Sample</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
First Year	119	74	30.13%
Second Year	50	31	12.66%
Third Year	43	27	10.89%
Fourth Year	33	20	8.36%
TOTAL	245	152	62.04%

Instrument

A Likert scale is a five-point scale that allows individuals to report their level of agreement or disagreement with a particular statement. A Likert scale (usually) presents her five alternative answers to a statement or question and allows respondents to indicate from positive to negative strength of agreement or sentiment regarding the question or statement (Mcleod, 2023).

This study will use a 5-point Likert scale to assess participants' self-assessment, study habits, numerical abilities, and mathematics learning productivity. The ratings given by participants for each statement were summed to calculate a total score representing attitudinal ratings. This method allowed us to quantitatively analyze participants' opinions regarding learning strategies, quality of instruction, and mathematical satisfaction. The Likert scale results can be used to determine the influence of participants' self-assessment, study habits, numerical abilities on mathematics learning productivity.

Procedure

In gathering data, the researcher observed the following steps.

Questionnaire Development. The researcher will search the questionnaires drawn from journal articles that are related to the four variables.

Revision and Validation of Questionnaires. After it is formed, a questionnaire used and submitted to a panel of experts to evaluate and

contextualize. The researcher follows the advice of those revision experts until it is approved for use.

Requesting Approval to Carry out the Study. The researcher had asked for permission to conduct this study from the Vice President for Academic Affairs of the research locale through a formal letter, which had been signed by the researcher himself and noted by his research adviser and the Director for Research and Development.

Distribution and Retrieval of the Questionnaire. Survey questionnaires in printed forms were distributed individually to the respondents, who were mathematics students roaming around the campus.

Collection and Tabulation of the Data. After the survey, the researcher took and analyzed the research instrument to record the collected data from the respondents. The statistical data were analyzed, and the findings were subsequently interpreted. Based on the final data set, conclusions were drawn, and recommendations were formulated in accordance with the results of the learning assessment.

Data Analysis

The data collected from the questionnaires were processed and analyzed using various statistical tools. These tools were applied to the data to help identify patterns and relationships that could shed light on the study's objectives. The results of this analysis were used to draw conclusions and make recommendations based on the findings.

Mean. This was used to describe the significant relationship between self- assessment, study habits, and numerical abilities on mathematics learning productivity among mathematics major students at Kapalong College of Agriculture, Sciences, and Technology.

Pearson-r. This statistical tool determined the significance of the relationship between self-assessment, study habits, and numerical abilities on mathematics learning productivity among mathematics major students at Kapalong College of Agriculture, Sciences, and Technology.

Regression. This was used to determine the significant influence of self- assessment, study habits, and numerical abilities on mathematics learning productivity among mathematics major students at Kapalong College of Agriculture, Sciences, and Technology.

Ethical Considerations

The study's participants were mathematics majors at Kapalong College of Agriculture, Sciences, and Technology, located in Maniki Kapalong, Davao del Norte. The researcher made sure to address and consider ethical considerations to ensure the study's soundness and integrity. This included obtaining informed consent from the participants, maintaining confidentiality, and avoiding any harm or discomfort for them. Furthermore, when conducting research with human respondents, the researcher adhered to the highest ethical standards. The primary goal of this quantitative investigation was to ensure that the study was ethically sound in order to protect the respondents' comfort. The researcher discussed how the study adhered to the guidelines outlined by Denzin and Lincoln (2011), which focused on three key principles: informed consent, risk of harm, anonymity and confidentiality, and conflict of interest.

Informed Consent. It is the first essential ethical principle to take into account. The obligations, the intended use of the data, and any potential consequences must be adequately disclosed to the respondents. The respondents must provide their explicit, active, and written consent in order to participate in the study. They must also state that they are aware of their right to access their information and that they are free to change their minds at any time. An agreement between the researcher and the respondents may be taken into account during the process of obtaining informed permission (Denzin & Lincoln, 2011).

To facilitate this, the researcher included a request for informed consent on the survey forms, asking participants if they were willing to participate despite any potential risks. If participants were uncertain or hesitant about agreeing, they were given the option to decline participation. The emphasis was on ensuring that participants made informed decisions and voluntarily chose to take part in the study.

During the process of obtaining informed consent, participants were informed of their rights. They were assured that they could withdraw from the study without providing a reason, decline to answer specific confidential questions, ask questions about the research, and be informed of the study's findings once the research was complete. These measures aimed to uphold ethical standards and ensure the well- being and rights of the participants throughout the research process.

Risk of Harm, Anonymity and Confidentiality. The respondent's information must always be kept confidential or hidden, and promises have to go further than just keeping their names private to include refraining from using identity remarks and material. Anonymity and secrecy are important steps in safeguarding people from possible harm (Denzin & Lincoln, 2011).

The careful disclosure of data to others posed potential risks in terms of social liabilities. Therefore, it was essential to ensure the confidentiality and security of the study's data to prevent a recurrence of such incidents. The researcher placed significant emphasis on safeguarding the safety, identity, and personal information of the respondents, recognizing the importance of their participation in the study. To establish a collection devoid of errors, the researcher eliminated personal identities from the data. The pristine data collection was devoid of any information that could potentially disclose the identities of the participants, such as personal names or residential addresses (such identifying information was stored separately in secure files located elsewhere). The data were retained and subsequently deleted three years following the completion of the study. These measures were implemented to uphold ethical standards and protect the rights and privacy of the study participants throughout and beyond the research process.

Conflict of Interest. Present connections or prior actions of the researcher may result in a conflict of interest, which needs to be reported transparently in an ethical committee application so that the committee may give advice on how to address the conflict (Fleming & Zegwaard, 2018). However, the study's researcher asserts that the research was carried out in the absence of any business or financial ties that may be interpreted as a possible conflict of interest.

This viewpoint holds that the research activity's findings were unaffected by outside factors because the respondents were also students, and the researcher had no competing interests with the study. Conflict of interest only arises when the researcher has the power to use coercive methods to force respondents to participate, such as threats of termination of benefits, blackmail, or other forms of punishment (e.g., principals threatening to fire teachers or teachers threatening to fail their students if they do not respond to the survey).

Results and Discussion

Presented in the section below are the discussion of the data on self-assessment, study habits, and numerical abilities on the mathematics learning productivity of mathematics students. The chapter presents the data on the following: the level of self-assessment of mathematics students; study habits; numerical abilities; the level of mathematics learning productivity; the significant relationship between self-assessment and mathematics learning productivity; the significant relationship between study habits and mathematics learning productivity; the significance relationship between numerical abilities and mathematics learning productivity; the significant influence between self-assessment and mathematics learning productivity; the significant influence between study habits and mathematics learning productivity and the significance influence between numerical abilities and mathematics learning productivity.

Level of Self-Assessment in terms of Previous Education and Expectations

The level self-assessment of the mathematics major students was measured through the survey questionnaire with the indicator previous education and expectation. The response of the respondents on each indicator were presented and analyzed below.

Presented in Table 2 is the level of self-assessment of mathematics major students in terms of previous education and expectation. The data revealed that the self-assessment of these students in terms of previous education and expectation had a total mean of 4.07 which means high. This indicated that the level of self-assessment in KCAST residing students in terms of previous education and expectation is oftentimes manifested.

The highest mean is 4.33 which descriptively means very high. This means that the item is always manifested by the respondents. This mean is from the item no. 2 – expecting to study mathematics on this course.

Further, the lowest mean is 3.67 but it can still be described as high. This means that the item is oftentimes manifested by the respondents. This mean is from the item no. 5 – having always done well in math classes.

Table 2. Level of Self-Assessment in terms of Previous Education and Expectations

<i>Previous Education and Expectations</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Description</i>
1. thinking i can pass the quizzes, tests and other assessments on mathematics courses.	3.88	High
2. expecting to study mathematics on this course.	4.33	Very High
3. being able to use my previous knowledge of solving math problems.	4.16	High
4. being open to dig more in learning mathematics.	4.30	Very High
5. having always done well in math classes.	3.67	High
Overall	4.07	High

Level of Self-Assessment in terms of Emotions and Confidence

The level of self-assessment of the mathematics major students was measured through the survey questionnaire with the indicator emotions and confidence. It was collected following specific guidelines and processes attaining the essential instrument for gathering the data. The response of the respondents on each indicator were presented and analyzed below.

Table 3. Level of Self-Assessment in terms of Emotions and Confidence

<i>Emotions and Confidence</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Description</i>
1. being generally confident about getting arithmetic calculations correct.	3.70	High
2. studying mathematics.	3.95	High
3. answering math problems.	3.95	High
4. being happy solving different mathematical problems and equations	3.94	High
5. feeling overwhelmed to see that I performed well in mathematics.	4.04	High
Overall	3.91	High

Presented in Table 3 is the level of self-assessment of mathematics major students in terms of emotions and confidence. The data revealed that the self-assessment of the students in terms of emotions and confidence had a total mean of 3.91 which means high. This indicated that the level self-assessment of mathematics major students in terms of emotions and confidence is oftentimes manifested.

The highest mean is 4.04 which descriptively means high. This means that the item is always manifested by the respondents. This mean is from the item no. 5 – feeling overwhelmed to see that I performed well in mathematics.

Further, the lowest mean is 3.70 but it can still be described as high. This means that the item is oftentimes manifested by the respondents. This mean is from the item no. 1 – being generally confident about getting arithmetic calculations correct

Level of Self-Assessment in Terms of General Abilities and Mathematical Awareness

The level of self-assessment of the mathematics major students was measured through the survey questionnaire with the indicator general abilities and mathematical awareness. It was collected following specific guidelines and processes attaining the essential instrument for gathering the data. The response of the respondents on each indicator were presented and analyzed below.

Presented in Table 4 is the level of self-assessment of mathematics major students in terms of general abilities and mathematical awareness. The data revealed that the level of self-assessment in terms of general abilities and mathematical awareness had a total mean of 3.72 which means high. This indicated that the level of self-assessment in KCAST in terms of general abilities and mathematical awareness is oftentimes manifested.

Table 4. *Level of Self-Assessment in Terms of General Abilities and Mathematical Awareness*

<i>General Abilities and Mathematical Awareness</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Description</i>
1. being generally good at mental arithmetic.	3.57	High
2. being able to solve math problems correctly.	3.59	High
3. calculating basic mathematics easily.	3.99	High
4. being able to interpret math problems.	3.74	High
5. doing arithmetic and telling if my answer looks correct or not.	3.72	High
Overall	3.72	High

The highest mean is 3.99 which descriptively means high. This means that the item is oftentimes manifested by the respondents. This mean is from the item no. 3– calculating basic mathematics easily.

Further, the lowest mean is 3.57 but it can still be described as high. This means that the item is oftentimes manifested by the respondents. This mean is from the items no. 1– being generally good at mental arithmetic.

Level of Self- Assessment in Terms of Self-assessment of Specific Mathematical Skills.

The level of self-assessment of the mathematics major students was measured through the survey questionnaire with the indicator self-assessment of specific mathematical skills. The response of the respondents on each indicator carefully were presented and analyzed below.

Presented in Table 5 is the level of self-assessment of mathematics major students in terms of self-assessment of specific mathematical skills. The data revealed that the self-assessment of mathematics major students in terms of self-assessment of specific mathematical skills had a total mean of 4.17 which means high. This indicated that the level of self-assessment of mathematics major students in terms of self-assessment of specific mathematical skills is oftentimes manifested.

Table 5. *Level of Self- Assessment in Terms of Self-assessment of Specific Mathematical Skills*

<i>Self-assessment of Specific Mathematical Skills</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Description</i>
1. multiplying or dividing numbers and know how to deal with negative numbers.	4.31	Very High
2. being able to identify and use integers to any mathematical expression.	4.14	High
3. solving algebraic expression and know how to express it in simplest form.	4.05	High
4. being able to name polygons.	4.16	High
5. knowing how to add and subtract fractions without a calculator.	4.19	High
Overall	4.17	High

The highest mean is 4.31 which descriptively means very high. This means that the item is always manifested by the respondents. This mean is from the item no. 4 – multiplying or dividing numbers and know how to deal with negative numbers.

Further, the lowest mean is 4.05 but it can still be described as high. This means that the item is oftentimes manifested by the respondents. This mean is from the item no. 3 – solving algebraic expression and know how to express it in simplest form.

Summary on the Level of Self-assessment

Presented in Table 6 is the overall level of Self-assessment of Mathematics major students in KCAST in terms of previous education and expectations, emotions and confidence, general abilities and mathematical awareness and self-assessment of specific mathematical skills. The data revealed that the level of self-assessment of students has a total mean of 3.97 with the descriptive equivalent of high. This indicated that the level of self-assessment of students is oftentimes manifested.

Table 6. Summary on the Level of Self-Assessment

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Description</i>
Previous Education and Expectations	4.07	High
Emotions and Confidence	3.91	High
General Abilities and Mathematical Awareness	3.72	High
Self-assessment of Specific Mathematical Skills	4.17	High
Overall	3.97	High

Further, the highest mean is 4.17 with the descriptive equivalent of high. This indicates that the level of self-assessment in terms self-assessment of specific mathematical skills is oftentimes manifested. In addition, the lowest is general abilities and mathematical awareness obtained a mean of 3.72 with a descriptive equivalent of high. This indicates that the level of self-assessment in terms of general abilities and mathematical awareness is manifested oftentimes.

Moreover, emotions and confidence obtained a mean of 3.91 with a descriptive equivalent of high. This indicates that the level of self-assessment in terms of emotions and confidence is oftentimes manifested.

Lastly, previous education and expectations obtained a mean of 4.07 with a descriptive equivalent of high. This indicates that the level of self-assessment in terms of previous education and expectations is oftentimes manifested.

Level of Study Habits in Terms of Note Taking

The level of study habits of the mathematics major students was measured through the survey questionnaire with the indicator note taking. The response of the respondents on each indicator were presented and analyzed below.

Presented in Table 7 is the study habits of the mathematics major students in terms of note taking. The data revealed that the level of study habits in terms of note taking had a total mean of 3.99 with a descriptive equivalent of high. This indicated that the level of study habits of the students in terms of note taking is oftentimes manifested.

Table 7. Level of Study Habits in Terms of Note Taking

<i>Note Taking</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Description</i>
1. using to listen attentively while taking down notes	4.01	High
2. paying attention in the class in order to take any important notes	4.09	High
3. having developed skills for effective note-taking during every lesson	4.01	High
4. taking down notes to preserve new knowledge	3.92	High
5. using symbols to express what my teacher says in the class	3.90	High
Overall	3.99	High

The highest mean is 4.09 which descriptively means high. This means that the item is of oftentimes manifested by the respondents. This mean is from the item no. 2 – paying attention in the class in order to take any important notes

On the other hand, the lowest mean is 3.90 but it can still be described as high. This means that the item is oftentimes manifested by the respondents. This mean is from the item no. 5 – using symbols to express what my teacher says in the class.

Level of Study Habits in Terms of Use of Library

The level of study habits of the mathematics major students was measured through the survey questionnaire with the indicator use of library. The response of the respondents on each indicator were presented and analyzed below.

Presented in Table 8 is the level study habits of the mathematics major students in terms of use of library. The data revealed that the level of study habits in terms of use of library had a total mean of 3.23 with a descriptive equivalent of moderate. This indicated that the level of study habits of the students in terms of use of library is sometimes manifested.

Table 8. Level of Study Habits in Terms of Use of Library

<i>Use of Library</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Description</i>
1. having devoted interest in library resources utilization.	3.51	High
2. studying in the library every day.	3.14	Moderate
3. using to do my assignment in the school library.	3.07	Moderate
4. feeling able to obtain a lot of information from the school library.	3.32	Moderate
5. seeking assistance from librarians and research assistants to navigate the library effectively and find relevant information.	3.09	Moderate
Overall	3.23	Moderate

The highest mean is 3.51 which descriptively means high. This means that the item is of oftentimes manifested by the respondents. This mean is from the item no. 1 – having devoted interest in library resources utilization.

On the other hand, the lowest mean is 3.07 described as moderate. This means that the item is sometimes manifested by the respondents. This mean is from the item no. 3 – using to do my assignment in the school library.

Level of Study Habits in Terms of Time Allocation to Study

The level of study habits of the mathematics major students was measured through the survey questionnaire with the indicator time allocation to study. The response of the respondents on each indicator were presented and analyzed below.

Presented in Table 9 is the level of study habits of the mathematics major students in terms of time allocation to study. The data revealed that the level of study habits on terms of time allocation to study had a total mean of 3.76 with a descriptive equivalent of high. This indicated that the level of study habits on terms of time allocation to study is oftentimes manifested.

The highest mean is 3.88 which descriptively means high. This means that the item is oftentimes manifested by the respondents. This mean is from the item no. 1 and 3 – having a space for studying, devoting extra time to thoroughly learn a certain subject like mathematics.

Table 9. *Level of Study Habits in Terms of Time allocation to study*

<i>Time Allocation to Study</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Description</i>
1. having a space for studying.	3.88	High
2. scheduling my time to cover all subjects.	3.84	High
3. devoting extra time to thoroughly learn a certain subject like mathematics.	3.88	High
4. using alarm clock to alert me for night reading.	3.55	High
5. setting up time for other social activities so that they will not interfere with my studies.	3.66	High
Overall	3.76	High

On the other hand, the lowest means are 3.55 but it can still be described as high. This mean that the items are oftentimes manifested by the respondents. This means are from the item 4 – using alarm clock to alert me for night reading.

Summary of the Level of Study Habits

Presented in Table 10 is the overall level of Study Habits of Mathematics major students in KCAST in terms of note taking, use of library, and time allocation to study.

The data revealed that the level of study habits of students has a total mean of 3.66 with the descriptive equivalent of high. This indicated that the level of study habits of students is oftentimes manifested.

Further, the highest mean is 3.99 with the descriptive equivalent of high. This indicates that the level of study habits in terms of note taking is oftentimes manifested. Furthermore, the lowest is use of library obtained a mean of 3.23 with a descriptive equivalent of moderate. This indicates that the level of study habits in terms of use of library is sometimes manifested.

Table 10. *Level of Study Habits*

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Description</i>
Note Taking	3.99	High
Use of Library	3.23	Moderate
Time Allocation to Study	3.76	High
Overall	3.66	High

Lastly, time allocation to study obtained a mean of 3.76 which descriptively means high. This indicates that the level of study habits in terms of time allocation to study is oftentimes manifested.

Level of Numerical Abilities in Terms of Numerical Reasoning

The level of numerical abilities of the mathematics major students was measured through the survey questionnaire with the indicator numerical reasoning. The response of the respondents on each indicator were presented and analyzed below.

Presented in Table 11 is the level of numerical abilities of the mathematics major students in terms of numerical reasoning. The data revealed that the level of numerical abilities in terms of numerical reasoning had a total mean of 3.78 with a descriptive equivalent of high. This indicated that the level of numerical abilities in terms of numerical reasoning is oftentimes manifested.

The highest mean is 3.88 which descriptively means high. This means that the item is of oftentimes manifested by the respondents. This mean is from the item no. 5 – feeling that my numerical reasoning skills have improved over time through practice and learning experiences.

On the other hand, the lowest means are 3.69 described as high. This means that these items are oftentimes manifested by the respondents. These means are from the items no. 4 – being able to identify relevant information and apply appropriate problem-solving strategies.

Table 11. *Level of Numerical Abilities in Terms of Numerical Reasoning*

<i>Numerical Reasoning</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Description</i>
1. feeling confident in my ability to solve mathematical problems involving numerical data.	3.80	High
2. believing I can effectively apply numerical reasoning skills to real- world situations and problems.	3.76	High
3. feeling comfortable interpreting charts, graphs, and numerical information presented in various formats.	3.75	High
4. being able to identify relevant information and apply appropriate problem-solving strategies.	3.69	High
5. feeling that my numerical reasoning skills have improved over time through practice and learning experiences.	3.88	High
Overall	3.78	High

Level of Numerical Abilities in Terms of Numerical Logic

The level of numerical abilities of the mathematics major students was measured through the survey questionnaire with the indicator numerical logic. The response of the respondents on each indicator were presented and analyzed below.

Presented in Table 12 is the level of numerical abilities of the mathematics major students in terms of numerical logic. The data revealed that the level of numerical abilities in terms of numerical logic had a total mean of 3.76 with a descriptive equivalent of high. This indicated that the level of numerical abilities in terms of numerical logic is oftentimes manifested.

The highest mean is 3.97 which descriptively means high. This means that the item is of oftentimes manifested by the respondents. This mean is from the item no. 1 – enjoying puzzles and problems that involve figuring out patterns and logical sequences.

Table 12. *Level of Numerical Abilities in Terms of Numerical Logic*

<i>Numerical Reasoning</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Description</i>
1. enjoying puzzles and problems that involve figuring out patterns and logical sequences.	3.97	High
2. believing can easily identify inconsistencies and fallacies in arguments and information presented using numbers.	3.73	High
3. being naturally break them down into smaller, logical steps and think systematically about all possibilities.	3.75	High
4. find it easy to identify cause-and- effect relationships between things expressed with numbers or data.	3.74	High
5. being skilled at predicting future outcomes or trends based on past numerical data and patterns.	3.61	High
Overall	3.76	High

On the other hand, the lowest means are 3.61 but it can still be described as high. This means that these items are oftentimes manifested by the respondents. These means are from the item no. 4 – being skilled at predicting future outcomes or trends based on past numerical data and patterns.

Level of Numerical Abilities in Terms of Numerical Arithmetic

The level of numerical abilities of the mathematics major students was measured through the survey questionnaire with the indicator numerical arithmetic. The response of the respondents on each indicator were presented and analyzed below.

Presented in Table 13 is the level of numerical abilities of the mathematics major students in terms of numerical arithmetic. The data revealed that the level of numerical abilities in terms of numerical arithmetic had a total mean of 3.89 with a descriptive equivalent of high. This indicated that the level of numerical abilities in terms of numerical arithmetic is oftentimes manifested.

Table 13. *Level of Numerical Abilities in Terms of Numerical Arithmetic*

<i>Numerical Arithmetic</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Description</i>
1. feeling confident and comfortable performing various types of arithmetic calculations (addition, subtraction, multiplication, division) quickly and accurately.	3.97	High
2. applying mathematical formulas and equations to solve practical problems efficiently.	3.88	High
3. making rarely mistakes when working with fractions, decimals, and percentages.	3.70	High
4. understanding the concepts of order of operations (PEMDAS) and can apply them correctly in complex calculations.	4.07	High
5. being able to estimate solutions to mathematical problems quickly and accurately without necessarily needing to perform the full calculation.	3.84	High
Overall	3.89	High

The highest mean is 4.07 which descriptively means high. This means that the item is oftentimes manifested by the respondents. This mean is from the item no. 4 – understanding the concepts of order of operations (PEMDAS) and can apply them correctly in complex calculations.

On the other hand, the lowest means are 3.70 but it can still be described as high. This means that these items are oftentimes manifested by the respondents. These means are from the items no. 3 – making rarely mistakes when working with fractions, decimals, and

percentages.

Level of Numerical Abilities in Terms of Numerical Estimation

The level of numerical abilities of the mathematics major students was measured through the survey questionnaire with the indicator numerical estimation. The response of the respondents on each indicator were presented and analyzed below.

Table 14. *Level of Numerical Abilities in Terms of Numerical Estimation*

<i>Numerical Arithmetic</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Description</i>
1. feeling good at approximating quantities and sizes without necessarily needing exact measurements.	3.68	High
2. being quickly judge the reasonableness of numerical information presented in texts, charts, or graphs.	3.67	High
3. having a good understanding of the relative magnitudes of different units (e.g., kilometers vs. meters) and can easily convert between them.	3.70	High
4. being able to effectively weigh the costs and benefits of different options using numerical information.	3.70	High
5. identifying outliers and inconsistencies in data sets and consider their impact on overall interpretations.	3.68	High
Overall	3.69	High

Presented in Table 14 is the level of numerical abilities of the mathematics major students in terms of numerical estimation. The data revealed that the level of numerical abilities in terms of numerical estimation had a total mean of 3.69 with a descriptive equivalent of high. This indicated that the level of numerical abilities in terms of numerical estimation is oftentimes manifested.

The highest mean is 3.70 which descriptively means high. This means that the item is of oftentimes manifested by the respondents. This mean is from the item no. 3 and 4 – having a good understanding of the relative magnitudes of different units (e.g., kilometers vs. meters) and can easily convert between them and being able to effectively weigh the costs and benefits of different options using numerical information.

On the other hand, the lowest means are 3.67 but it can still be described as high. This means that these items are oftentimes manifested by the respondents. These means are from the items no. 2– being quickly judge the reasonableness of numerical information presented in texts, charts, or graphs.

Level of Numerical Abilities in Terms of Data Interpretation

The level of numerical abilities of the mathematics major students was measured through the survey questionnaire with the indicator data interpretation. The response of the respondents on each indicator were presented and analyzed below.

Presented in Table 15 is the level of numerical abilities of the mathematics major students in terms of data interpretation. The data revealed that the level of numerical abilities in terms of data interpretation had a total mean of 3.84 with a descriptive equivalent of high. This indicated that the level of numerical abilities in terms of data interpretation is oftentimes manifested.

The highest mean is 3.96 which descriptively means high. This means that the item is of oftentimes manifested by the respondents. This mean is from the item no. 1 – being able to effectively read and understand information presented in tables, charts, and graphs

On the other hand, the lowest means are 3.76 but it can still be described as high. This means that these items are oftentimes manifested by the respondents. These means are from the items no. 3 – drawing valid conclusions from data and avoid making unsupported generalizations.

Table 15. *Level of Numerical Abilities in Terms of Data Interpretation*

<i>Data Interpretation</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Description</i>
1. being able to effectively read and understand information presented in tables, charts, and graphs	3.96	High
2. identifying the main trends and patterns in data sets and explain their meaning in clear and concise language.	3.83	High
3. drawing valid conclusions from data and avoid making unsupported generalizations.	3.76	High
4. being aware of potential biases and limitations in data collection and analysis and can consider them when interpreting results.	3.81	High
5. using data to support my arguments and make informed decisions in various situations.	3.86	High
Overall	3.84	High

Summary of the Level of Numerical Abilities

Presented in Table 16 is the overall level of Numerical Abilities of Mathematics major students in KCAST in terms of numerical reasoning, numerical logic, numerical arithmetic, numerical estimation, and data interpretation. The data revealed that the level of numerical abilities of students has a total mean of 3.79 with the descriptive equivalent of high. This indicated that the level of numerical abilities of students is oftentimes manifested.

Further, the highest mean is 3.89 with the descriptive equivalent of high. This indicates that the level of numerical abilities in terms of

numerical arithmetic is oftentimes manifested.

Furthermore, the lowest is numerical estimation obtained a mean of 3.69 with a descriptive equivalent of high. This indicates that the level of numerical abilities in terms of numerical estimation is oftentimes manifested.

Table 16. *Level of Numerical Abilities*

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Description</i>
Numerical Reasoning	3.78	High
Numerical Logic	3.76	High
Numerical Arithmetic	3.89	High
Numerical Estimation	3.69	High
Data Interpretation	3.84	High
Overall	3.79	High

In addition, numerical logic obtained a mean of 3.76 with a descriptive equivalent of high. This indicates that the level of numerical abilities in terms of numerical logic is oftentimes manifested.

Moreover, numerical reasoning obtained a mean of 3.78 with a descriptive equivalent of high. This indicates that the level of numerical abilities in terms of numerical reasoning is oftentimes manifested.

Lastly, data interpretation obtained a mean of 3.84 with a descriptive equivalent of high. This indicates that the level of numerical abilities in terms of data interpretation is oftentimes manifested.

Level of Mathematics Learning Productivity in terms of Persistence

The level of mathematics learning productivity of the mathematics major students was measured through the survey questionnaire with the indicator persistence. The response of the respondents on each indicator were presented and analyzed below.

Presented in Table 17 is the level of mathematics learning productivity of the mathematics major students in terms of persistence. The data revealed that the level of mathematics learning productivity in terms of persistence had a total mean of 3.94 with a descriptive equivalent of high. This indicated that the level of mathematics learning productivity in terms of persistence is oftentimes manifested.

Table 17. *Level of Mathematics Learning Productivity in terms of Persistence*

<i>Persistence</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Description</i>
1. being consistently push through challenging mathematical problems, even when they initially seem difficult.	3.89	High
2. feeling determined to understand mathematical concepts thoroughly, even if it requires extra time and effort.	3.93	High
3. maintaining my focus and concentration during mathematics learning sessions, avoiding distractions	3.88	High
4. being persistently revisit and review mathematical topics to reinforce my understanding over time	3.90	High
5. believing that consistent effort and perseverance are key to improving my mathematical skills.	4.07	High
Overall	3.94	High

The highest mean is 4.07 which descriptively means high. This means that the item is of oftentimes manifested by the respondents. This mean is from the item no. 5 – believing that consistent effort and perseverance are key to improving my mathematical skills

On the other hand, the lowest means are 3.88 described as high. This means that these items are oftentimes manifested by the respondents. These means are from the items no. 3– maintaining my focus and concentration during mathematics learning sessions, avoiding distractions.

Level of Mathematics Learning Productivity in terms of Engagement

The level of mathematics learning productivity of the mathematics major students was measured through the survey questionnaire with the indicator engagement. The response of the respondents on each indicator were presented and analyzed below.

Table 18. *Level of Mathematics Learning Productivity in terms of Engagement*

<i>Engagement</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Description</i>
1. finding the activities and exercises in my mathematics learning materials interesting and engaging	3.99	High
2. being actively participate in class discussions and group activities related to mathematics.	3.79	High
3. enjoying exploring and solving mathematical problems, considering them as enjoyable challenges	3.92	High
4. feeling motivated to delve deeper into mathematical concepts beyond what is required in the curriculum	3.95	High
5. being actively seek out additional resources or materials to enhance my understanding of mathematical topic	3.98	High
Overall	3.93	High

Presented in Table 18 is the level of mathematics learning productivity of the mathematics major students in terms of engagement. The data revealed that the level of mathematics learning productivity in terms of engagement had a total mean of 3.93 with a descriptive equivalent of high. This indicated that the level of mathematics learning productivity in terms of engagement is oftentimes manifested.

The highest mean is 3.99 which descriptively means high. This means that the item is of oftentimes manifested by the respondents. This mean is from the item no. 1 – finding the activities and exercises in my mathematics learning materials interesting and engaging

On the other hand, the lowest means are 3.79 described as high. This means that these items are oftentimes manifested by the respondents. These means are from the items no. 2 – being actively participate in class discussions and group activities related to mathematics.

Level of Mathematics Learning Productivity in terms of Collaboration

Table 19. *Level of Mathematics Learning Productivity in terms of Collaboration*

<i>Collaboration</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Description</i>
1. believing that working collaboratively with peers enhances my understanding of mathematical concepts	4.21	High
2. being actively contribute to group projects and discussions in my mathematics class.	4.08	High
3. appreciating the diverse perspectives and approaches that my peers bring to solving mathematical problems.	4.13	High
4. being open to seeking help from classmates and enjoy collaborating with them on challenging mathematical tasks.	4.11	High
5. believing that group activities and collaborative learning contribute positively to my overall mathematics learning experience.	4.15	High
Overall	4.14	High

The level of mathematics learning productivity of the mathematics major students was measured through the survey questionnaire with the indicator collaboration. The response of the respondents on each indicator were presented and analyzed below.

Presented in Table 19 is the level of mathematics learning productivity of the mathematics major students in terms of persistence. The data revealed that the level of mathematics learning productivity in terms of collaboration had a total mean of 4.14 with a descriptive equivalent of high. This indicated that the level of mathematics learning productivity in terms of collaboration is oftentimes manifested.

The highest mean is 4.21 which descriptively means high. This means that the item is of oftentimes manifested by the respondents. This mean is from the item no. 1 – believing that working collaboratively with peers enhances my understanding of mathematical concepts.

On the other hand, the lowest means are 4.08 described as high. This means that these items are oftentimes manifested by the respondents. These means are from the items no. 2 – being actively contribute to group projects and discussions in my mathematics class.

Level of Mathematics Learning Productivity in terms of Communication

The level of mathematics learning productivity of the mathematics major students was measured through the survey questionnaire with the indicator communication. The response of the respondents on each indicator were presented and analyzed below.

Table 20. *Level of Mathematics Learning Productivity in terms of Communication*

<i>Communication</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Description</i>
1. feeling comfortable expressing my thoughts and ideas about mathematical concepts in class discussions.	3.86	High
2. being actively seek clarification from my teachers or peers when I encounter challenges in understanding mathematical topics	3.84	High
3. believing that effective communication is essential for successful group work and collaborative problem-solving in mathematics	4.14	High
4. using various forms of communication (verbal, written, visual) to explain my mathematical reasoning to others	4.07	High
5. being actively listen to the perspectives and explanations of others during mathematics discussions.	4.11	High
Overall	4.00	High

Presented in Table 20 is the level of mathematics learning productivity of the mathematics major students in terms of communication. The data revealed that the level of mathematics learning productivity in terms of communication had a total mean of 4.00 with a descriptive equivalent of high. This indicated that the level of mathematics learning productivity in terms of persistence is oftentimes manifested.

The highest mean is 4.14 which descriptively means high. This means that the item is of oftentimes manifested by the respondents. This mean is from the item no. 3 – believing that effective communication is essential for successful group work and collaborative problem-solving in mathematics On the other hand, the lowest means are 3.84 described as high. This means that these items are

oftentimes manifested by the respondents. These means are from the items no. 2 – being actively seek clarification from my teachers or peers when I encounter challenges in understanding mathematical topics.

Summary of the Level of Numerical Abilities

Presented in Table 21 is the overall level of Mathematics Learning Productivity major students in KCAST in terms of persistence, engagement, collaboration and communication. The data revealed that the level of mathematics learning productivity of students has a total mean of 4.00 with the descriptive equivalent of high. This indicated that the level of mathematics learning productivity of students is oftentimes manifested.

Further, the highest mean is 4.14 with the descriptive equivalent of high. This indicates that the level of mathematics learning productivity in terms collaboration is oftentimes manifested.

Table 21. *Level of Numerical Abilities*

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Description</i>
Persistence	3.94	High
Engagement	3.93	High
Collaboration	4.14	High
Communication	4.00	High
Overall	4.00	High

Furthermore, the lowest is numerical estimation obtained a mean of 3.93 with a descriptive equivalent of high. This indicates that the level of mathematics learning productivity in terms engagement is oftentimes manifested.

In addition, persistence obtained a mean of 3.94 with a descriptive equivalent of high. This indicates that the level of mathematics learning productivity in terms persistence is oftentimes manifested.

Lastly, communication obtained a mean of 4.00 with a descriptive equivalent of high. This indicates that the level of mathematics learning productivity in terms communication is oftentimes manifested.

Significant Relationship Between Self-Assessment and Mathematics Learning Productivity

Table 22. *Significant Relationship Between Self-Assessment and Mathematics Learning Productivity*

<i>Variable</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>R-Value</i>	<i>P-Value</i>	<i>Decision @=0.05</i>
Self-Assessment	3.97	.713	<.001	Ho Rejected
Mathematics Learning Productivity	4.00			

Presented in Table 22 was the significant relationship between self- assessment and mathematics learning productivity. The p-value is less than 0.05 which we could indicate the significant relationship between self-assessment and mathematics learning productivity of mathematics major students. This is also a profound indication about the rejection of the null hypothesis about there is significant relationship between self-assessment and mathematics learning productivity.

Significant Relationship Between Study Habits and Mathematics Learning Productivity

Presented in Table 23 was the significant relationship between study habits and mathematics learning productivity. The p-value is less than 0.05 which we could indicate the significant relationship between study habits and mathematics learning productivity of mathematics major students. This is also a profound indication about the rejection of the null hypothesis about there is significant relationship between study habits and mathematics learning productivity.

Table 23. *Significant Relationship Between Study Habits and Mathematics Learning Productivity*

<i>Variable</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>R-Value</i>	<i>P-Value</i>	<i>Decision @=0.05</i>
Study Habits	3.66	.663	<.001	Ho Rejected
Mathematics Learning Productivity	4.00			

Significant Relationship Between Numerical Abilities and Mathematics Learning Productivity

Presented in Table 24 was the significant relationship between numerical abilities and mathematics learning productivity. The p-value is less than 0.05 which we could indicate the significant relationship between numerical abilities and mathematics learning productivity of mathematics major students. This is also a profound indication about the rejection of the null hypothesis about there is significant relationship between numerical abilities and mathematics learning productivity.

Table 24. Significant Relationship Between Numerical Abilities and Mathematics Learning Productivity

Variable	Mean	R-Value	P-Value	Decision @=0.05
Numerical Abilities	3.79	.762	<.001	Ho Rejected
Mathematics Learning Productivity	4.00			

Domain/s of Numerical Abilities That Can Influence Mathematics Learning Productivity

Table 25. Domain/s of Self-Assessment That Can Influence Mathematics Learning Productivity

Independent Variables	Unstandardized Coefficients	Standardized Coefficients	P-Value	Decision @=0.05
Self-assessment	Beta	Std. Error	Beta	
(Constant)	4	0.045		
Previous Education and Expectations	0.113	0.089	0.11	0.205 Ho Accepted
Emotions and Confidence	0.171	0.083	0.188	0.042 Ho Rejected
General Abilities and Mathematical Awareness	0.186	0.078	0.211	0.017 Ho Rejected
Self-Assessment of Specific Mathematical Skills	0.317	0.069	0.345	< .001 Ho Rejected

Dependent Variable: Mathematics Learning Productivity

Note: R= 0.720, R2=0.519, F-ratio= 39.669 P-value= <.001

Presented in Table 25 was the significant influence of the domain/s of self- assessment that can influence mathematics learning productivity among mathematics major students in KCAST. The results showed that the emotions and confidence, a domain of mathematics learning productivity, appears to be a statistically significant predictor of the level of self-assessment of mathematics major students in KCAST, ($\beta=0.171$, $p<.042$). At 0.05 level of significance, the null hypothesis is rejected. The beta value indicates that for every units increase of emotions and confidence, the level of mathematics learning productivity mathematics major students will also increase by 0.171 units.

Moreover, the results showed that general abilities and mathematical awareness, a domain of mathematics learning productivity, appears to be significant predictor of the level of self-assessment of mathematics major students in KCAST, ($\beta=0.186$ $p<.017$). At 0.05 level of significance, the null hypothesis is rejected.

In addition, the P-value of one domain, self-assessment of specific mathematical skills ($\beta=0.317$, $p<.001$). At 0.05 level of significance, the P-value of the one domain exceeded 0.05. This suggest that the one domain which self-assessment of specific mathematical skills have a significant influence on mathematics learning productivity.

Subsequently, the P-value of one remaining domain, previous education and expectations ($\beta=0.113$, $p=.205$). At 0.05 level of significance, the P-value of the one domain exceeded 0.05. This suggest that the one domain which is evaluation do not have significant influence on students’ mathematics learning productivity.

Moreover, self-assessment explained a significant proportion of variance in mathematics learning productivity, $R^2= 0.519$, $F= 39.669$, $p<0.01$. The R^2 of 0.519 shows that the model predicts 51.9% of the statistical variation observed in the level of student’s mathematics learning productivity among the respondents. The coefficient of alienation which 48.1 points to the extent at which other indicators or domains not included in the study may explain the variance observed in the level of students’ mathematics learning productivity among the respondents.

Domain/s Of Study Habits That Can Influence Mathematics Learning Productivity

Table 26. Domain/s of Study Habits That Can Influence Mathematics Learning Productivity

Independent Variables	Unstandardized Coefficients	Standardized Coefficients	P-Value	Decision @=0.05
Study Habits	Beta	Std. Error	Beta	
(Constant)	4	0.045		
Note Taking	0.196	0.052	0.263	< .001 Ho Rejected
Use of Library	0.076	0.045	0.12	0.094 Ho Accepted
Time Allocation to Study	0.337	0.06	0.438	< .001 Ho Rejected

Dependent Variable: Mathematics Learning Productivity

Note: R= 0.686 R2=0.471, F-ratio= 43.895 P-value= <.001

Presented in Table 26 was the significant influence of the domain/s of study habits that can influence mathematics learning productivity among mathematics major students in KCAST. The results showed that the note taking, a domain of mathematics learning productivity, appears to be a statistically significant predictor of the level of study habits of mathematics major students in KCAST, ($\beta=0.196$,

$p < .001$). At 0.05 level of significance, the null hypothesis is rejected. The beta value indicates that for every unit increase of note taking, the level of mathematics learning productivity mathematics major students will also increase by 0.196 units.

Moreover, the results showed that time allocation to study, a domain of mathematics learning productivity, appears to be significant predictor of the level of study habits of mathematics major students in KCAST, ($\beta = 0.337$, $p < .001$). At 0.05 level of significance, the null hypothesis is rejected.

Furthermore, study habits explained a significant proportion of variance in mathematics learning productivity, $R^2 = 0.471$, $F = 43.895$, $p < .001$. The R^2 of 0.471 shows that the model predicts 47.1% of the statistical variation observed in the level of student's mathematics learning productivity among the respondents. The coefficient of alienation which 52.9 points to the extent at which other indicators or domains not included in the study may explain the variance observed in the level of students' mathematics learning productivity among the respondents.

Domain/s of Numerical Abilities That Can Influence Mathematics Learning Productivity

Table 27. Domain/s of Numerical Abilities That Can Influence Mathematics Learning Productivity

<i>Numerical Abilities</i>	<i>Beta</i>	<i>Std. Error</i>	<i>Beta</i>	<i>P-Value</i>	<i>Decision @ = 0.05</i>
(Constant)	4	0.045			
Numerical Reasoning	0.175	0.077	0.192	0.024	Ho Rejected
Numerical Logic	0.093	0.069	0.107	0.175	Ho Accepted
Numerical Arithmetic	0.109	0.078	0.12	0.162	Ho Accepted
Numerical Estimation	-0.047	0.079	-0.057	0.549	Ho Accepted
Data Interpretation	0.43	0.076	0.51	< .001	Ho Rejected

Dependent Variable: Mathematics Learning Productivity

Note: $R = 0.787$, $R^2 = 0.620$, $F\text{-ratio} = 47.596$ $P\text{-value} = < .001$

Presented in Table 27 was the significant influence of the domain/s of numerical abilities that can influence mathematics learning productivity among mathematics major students in KCAST. The results showed that the numerical reasoning, a domain of mathematics learning productivity, appears to be a statistically significant predictor of the level of numerical abilities of mathematics major students in KCAST, ($\beta = 0.175$, $p = 0.024$). At 0.05 level of significance, the null hypothesis is rejected. The beta value indicates that for every unit increase of numerical reasoning, the level of mathematics learning productivity mathematics major students will also increase by 0.175 units.

Moreover, the results showed that data interpretation, a domain of mathematics learning productivity, appears to be significant predictor of the level of numerical abilities of mathematics major students in KCAST, ($\beta = 0.43$, $p < .001$). At 0.05 level of significance, the null hypothesis is rejected.

In addition, the P-value of one domain, numerical logic, ($\beta = 0.093$, $p = 0.107$). At 0.05 level of significance, the P-value of the one domain exceeded 0.05. This suggest that the one domain which is numerical logic do not have significant influence on student's mathematics learning productivity.

Subsequently, the P-value of one remaining domain, numerical arithmetic ($\beta = 0.109$, $p = 0.162$). At 0.05 level of significance, the P-value of the one domain exceeded 0.05. This suggest that the one domain which is numerical arithmetic do not have significant influence on student's mathematics learning productivity.

Furthermore, the P-value of one remaining domain, numerical estimation ($\beta = -0.047$, $p = 0.549$). At 0.05 level of significance, the P-value of the one domain exceeded 0.05. This suggest that the one domain which is numerical estimation do not have significant influence on student's mathematics learning productivity.

Moreover, numerical abilities explained a significant proportion of variance in mathematics learning productivity, $R^2 = 0.620$, $F = 47.596$, $p < .001$. The R^2 of 0.620 shows that the model predicts 62% of the statistical variation observed in the level of student's mathematics learning productivity among the respondents. The coefficient of alienation which 38 points to the extent at which other indicators or domains not included in the study may explain the variance observed in the level of students' mathematics learning productivity among the respondents.

Conclusions

Based on the findings of the study, conclusions were drawn in answer to questions raised in the previous chapter. The respondents reported a high level of self- assessment which means that the variable is oftentimes observed by the students.

Based on the results in study habits of mathematics major students, it can be also drawn that the level of study habits among students was in high. This means that the students oftentimes manifested the variable.

In addition, the results in numerical abilities of mathematics major students, it can be also drawn that the level of numerical abilities among students was in high. This means that the students oftentimes manifested the variable.

Moreover, based on the results in mathematics learning productivity of the mathematics major students, it can be also drawn that the level of mathematics learning productivity of the students was in high. Also, this means that the students oftentimes manifested the variable.

Overall correlation of two variables reveals a significant relationship between the two variables which was self-assessment and mathematics learning productivity of the mathematics major students. The study shows that the self-assessment has a high, positive, and significant relationship with mathematics learning productivity of the students, which means that the first null hypothesis proposed in the study is rejected.

Overall correlation of two variables reveals a significant relationship between the two variables which was study habits and mathematics learning productivity of the mathematics major students. The study shows that the study habits has a high, positive, and significant relationship with mathematics learning productivity of the students, which means that the first null hypothesis proposed in the study is rejected.

Overall correlation of two variables reveals a significant relationship between the two variables which was numerical abilities and mathematics learning productivity of the mathematics major students. The study shows that the numerical abilities has a high, positive, and significant relationship with mathematics learning productivity of the students, which means that the first null hypothesis proposed in the study is rejected.

Based on the result of regression analysis, three domains have shown significant influence to the self-assessment. This means that the domains – emotions and confidence, general abilities and mathematical awareness, self-assessment of specific mathematical skills– is the significant predictor of mathematics learning productivity of the mathematics major students. This also indicates the rejection of the second null hypothesis proposed in the study. Accordingly, the model describes 51.9% of the statistical variation in the level of self-assessment of the respondents, while the remaining 48.1% refers to other variables that have not been included in the study that also affect the mathematics learning productivity of the respondents.

Based on the result of regression analysis, two domains have shown significant influence to the study habits. This means that the domains –note taking and time allocation to study – is the significant predictor of mathematics learning productivity of the mathematics major students. This also indicates the rejection of the second null hypothesis proposed in the study. Accordingly, the model describes 47.1% of the statistical variation in the level of study habits of the respondents, while the remaining 52.1% refers to other variables that have not been included in the study that also affect the mathematics learning productivity of the respondents.

Based on the result of regression analysis, two domains have shown significant influence to the numerical abilities. This means that the domains –numerical reasoning and data interpretation– is the significant predictor of mathematics learning productivity of the mathematics major students. This also indicates the rejection of the second null hypothesis proposed in the study. Accordingly, the model describes 62% of the statistical variation in the level of numerical abilities of the respondents, while the remaining 38% refers to other variables that have not been included in the study that also affect the mathematics learning productivity of the respondents.

The study findings reveal significant correlations and predictors of mathematics learning productivity among mathematics major students. Notably, high levels of self - assessment, study habits, and numerical abilities were observed among the respondents, indicating their frequent manifestation of these variables. The study demonstrates that self-assessment, study habits, and numerical abilities each have a high, positive, and significant relationship with mathematics learning productivity, rejecting the respective null hypotheses. Regression analysis identifies specific domains within each factor that significantly influence mathematics learning productivity, such as emotions and confidence, general abilities and mathematical awareness, self-assessment of specific mathematical skills for self-assessment; note- taking and time allocation to study for study habits; and numerical reasoning and data interpretation for numerical abilities. These results collectively suggest the importance of addressing these domains to enhance mathematics learning productivity among students, while acknowledging the influence of other variables not included in the study.

Based on the previously mentioned findings from the study, the following recommendations were formulated. Among the mathematics learning productivity, it was found that content has the lowest mean. Therefore, the following recommendations are given.

It is hereby recommended for improving the productivity of mathematics learning could be to promote regular practice sessions with a range of problem kinds and levels of difficulty. Providing students with opportunity to participate in interactive online resources or manipulatives can improve their comprehension and recall of mathematical ideas. Furthermore, showing children how math is relevant to their daily lives through real-world examples and applications can motivate them to learn more efficiently. Furthermore, encouraging an environment in the classroom where students feel free to ask questions and make mistakes will help them become more confident and open to participating in the learning process. All things considered, teachers can help students become more productive learners of mathematics by implementing these tactics.

Based on the result, the general abilities and mathematical awareness has been identified as having the lowest mean among the self-assessment indicator. Consequently, a set of targeted recommendations was formulated to improve and strengthen this specific aspect.

Several targeted recommendations were proposed to address and enhance this aspect.

Therefore, it is hereby recommended that building a solid foundation in fundamental mathematical concepts such as addition, subtraction, multiplication, and division is crucial for developing general talents and mathematical awareness. To become proficient in these abilities, which serve as the foundation for more complex mathematical ideas, practice and repetition are essential. Furthermore, developing one's capacity for critical analysis and problem-solving can significantly improve one's mathematical awareness. Playing games like brainteasers and puzzles that demand logical reasoning and analytical thinking might help hone these abilities. Through emphasizing both general skills and quantitative knowledge, people can create a strong foundation for addressing a variety of obstacles in different spheres of life.

The findings revealed that use of library resulted in the lowest mean among study habits indicators. The findings emphasize the need for improvement in the use of library of the student. Therefore, the following recommendation are given.

It is hereby recommended that the organization think about creating and promoting collaborative learning areas in the library. These areas can promote conversations, study sessions, and knowledge exchanges. Peer-to-peer learning and community building allow students to improve their study habits and acquire knowledge from a variety of viewpoints. Plan frequent orientation programs for students to acquaint them with the materials and services offered by the library.

In addition, the numerical estimation has been identified as having the lowest mean among the self-assessment indicator. Consequently, a set of targeted recommendations was formulated to improve and strengthen this specific aspect. Several targeted recommendations were proposed to address and enhance this aspect.

It is hereby recommended a hands-on attitude, it should be emphasized how important it is to divide complicated problems into smaller, more manageable components, estimate each component separately, and then combine the estimates to get an overall estimate. Promote the use of well-known reference points for estimating and comparison, such as common measurements or objects from daily life. The importance of practice and iteration in improving one's estimate skills over time cannot be overstated. People can acquire more precise and dependable estimate skills that are helpful in a variety of real-world situations by encouraging an attitude of curiosity and experimenting.

Moreover, it is recommended for future researchers to explore the same topic using various methodologies, such as mixed methods, qualitative approaches, or case studies, in order to provide a more comprehensive understanding of the importance of the relationships between the variables.

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